

PECULIARITIES OF NURSING CARE IN GERONTOLOGY

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Abstract

In the human body, from birth to death, continuous morphological, chemical, physiological, psychological changes are observed. Scientists have been aging since ancient times. Philosophical debates about the causes and mysteries of eternity conducted. Its roots go back to ancient Chinese and Indian scientists reflected in his works, Hippocrates' collections and Ibn Sina's "Tib Qonunlari". found. The main goal of "nursing care for the elderly" is active and is to find ways to prolong his full life. For elderly patients To serve, because it is the daily task of most medical workers 25–30% of all patients in need are elderly patients. Everyone in the world Demographic indicators in the countries are increasing at the expense of the elderly. Aging processes, the process of diseases in the rocks and caring for the elderly. We will cover issues such as processes in our current article.

Key words: Gerontology, aging, nursing process, physiological view, general biological process, cytoplasm, membranes, mitochondria, heterochronic aging, heterotopic property.

"Aging" is closely related to medical biology, it is a molecule and studies the causes of aging of the whole organism, starting from the cells. Physiological aging It is determined by maintaining mental and physical health, a certain level of work ability, enthusiasm, and interest in the surrounding events. The influence of the external environment and the body's internal factors accelerate the aging process, the body is premature leads to aging, this process after the growth and development of the organism has stopped begins. Aging is a multifocal biological process in which cells in the nucleus, cytoplasm, membranes, mitochondria and other structures

appears. 4 different characteristics are distinguished in the development of the aging process: Heterochrony; Heterotopy; Heterokinetics; Heterocatheftenty.

The nursing process is a goal-oriented, flexible process. Nurses work in hospitals, families, nursing homes, polyclinics will go. In this process, the nurse uses her knowledge, talent, experience and the ability to think logically, to restore the health of the patient, to take care of him, it is necessary to spend on solving their problems. The nursing process consists of 5 stages:

Stage 1. Data collection, analysis and evaluation. This is a person performed to identify problems and plan care. At this stage monitor the patient's condition - from himself, relatives, acquaintances, medical card is to collect information. As of the information collected at this stage, none not concluded. But to know the patient's problem, the disease in him along with objective and subjective symptoms, the main need of the patient is determined. So, in communication with the patient, we are comprehensive in order to know his basic needs we need to use specialist communication.

Stage 2. Nursing diagnosis. That is, to the etiology of the disease and clinical symptoms Based on this, the main problem of the patient is identified and defined. "Nurse diagnosis" is the basis of the nursing process. The purpose of nursing diagnosis is to is to make a correct assessment of the patient's condition and course of the disease.

Stage 3. Plan ways to solve the problem. As far as planning is possible carried out together with the patient. The nurse eases the patient's condition, illness prevention of complications, that is, a plan to solve the patient's health problems and records it on the nurse's observation card.

Step 4. Perform the planned task and document it. This patient care and transfer information to the nurse on duty is to record the process.

Step 5. Based on the final result, summary assessment or care plan to evaluate whether or not a positive result was obtained from the work done, if necessary, change the nursing diagnosis and create another plan and treatment based on the new diagnosis is to be carried out on this basis.

In short, a mature nurse who can meet the demands of today's times Relying on the science of "gerontology", the elderly are cared for not only during illness, but also adapting to the physiological aging process, continuing full life activities must be an assistant specialist. When seniors seek medical care, recognizing them as equal members of society and giving them special respect and honor it is necessary to show.

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